

Protac technology of degrading unhealthy proteins- a futuristic approach therapy for Alzheimer's and Cancer disorders

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Abstract- In recent decades, a promising therapeutic strategy called Proteolysis-Targeting Chimera (PROTAC) therapy has emerged as a potential breakthrough in the field of drug development. PROTACs are bifunctional molecules designed to degrade disease-associated proteins by harnessing the cellular machinery responsible for protein turnover. Alzheimer's disease and cancer are two devastating and prevalent diseases have limited treatment options. In Alzheimer's disease, the accumulation of misfolded proteins, such as amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) and tau, contributes to the neurodegenerative processes. Current therapeutic strategies for Alzheimer's disease focus on reducing the levels of these protein aggregates. Preclinical studies utilizing PROTACs against $A\beta$ and tau have demonstrated promising results in promoting protein clearance and improving cognitive function in animal models, suggesting their therapeutic potential for Alzheimer's disease. In the realm of cancer treatment, aberrant protein expression or dysregulated signalling pathways often drive tumorigenesis. Traditional cancer therapies typically target these proteins directly. However, acquired resistance and off-target effects limit the efficacy of such treatments. PROTAC therapy provides a new avenue by inducing the degradation of disease-driving proteins, offering the advantage of targeting proteins that were previously considered "undruggable." Several PROTACs have shown efficacy in degrading oncogenic proteins, leading to tumor regression and improved outcomes in preclinical models and early-phase clinical trials. Despite the enormous potential of PROTAC therapy, several challenges remain. Optimization of PROTAC design, such as enhancing target selectivity and stability, is crucial for its successful clinical translation. Nevertheless, PROTAC therapy represents a promising and innovative strategy for the treatment of both Alzheimer's disease and cancer treatment. This review aims to provide an overview of the application of PROTAC therapy in both Alzheimer's disease and cancer, highlighting its potential as a transformative treatment approach.

Keywords: PROTAC therapy; Alzheimer's disease; Cancer; Protein degradation; Neurodegeneration; Tumorigenesis.

INTRODUCTION

Proteolysis-targeting chimaera (PROTAC) therapy is a type of targeted medicine that is designed to selectively degrade disease-causing proteins within cells. This innovative approach utilises a bifunctional molecule that binds to the target protein and recruits an E3 ubiquitin ligase enzyme, resulting in the degradation of the target protein [1]. The traditional approach to drug development involves the design of small molecules that selectively bind to the target protein and inhibit its function. However, identifying drugs that selectively bind to specific targets can be challenging due to similarities in the binding pockets of structurally similar proteins, leading to off-target effects and toxicity. Moreover, drugs that target protein-protein interactions are also challenging to design since the interface between the two proteins is often large and flat. This approach offers a novel solution to these challenges [2]. Human cells have a natural mechanism to dispose of proteins that are mutated, misfolded, or no longer needed. E3 ubiquitin ligases recognise proteins to be degraded and repeatedly tag them with ubiquitin molecules carried by E2 ubiquitin-conjugating enzymes. Their repeated actions form chains of ubiquitin tags that direct proteins to the proteasome, an intracellular complex that degrades proteins. Protacs harness this naturally occurring machinery and degrade specific disease-causing proteins, including proteins not treated by traditional drugs [3].

Proteolysis-targeting chimaeras are a new class of small molecules that have gained attention for their promising potential in the development of targeted protein degradation-based therapies for a range of diseases, including neurodegenerative diseases, autoimmune diseases, cancer, etc, [Fig. 2]. PROTACs are designed to specifically target unwanted proteins and induce their degradation, offering a highly targeted approach to therapy with fewer side

effects. In Alzheimer's treatment, PROTACs have the potential to target amyloid and tau proteins, which are critical factors in the formation of brain plaque linked to the disease. In cancer, PROTACs have shown promising results in targeting tumour suppressor proteins and oncogenes, leading to the inhibition of tumour growth. Although there are still obstacles to overcome in designing and testing PROTACs for clinical use, their potential benefits make them an exciting area of research with the potential to transform medical treatment [4-5].

PROTAC (proteolysis-targeting chimeras)

PROTAC, or targeted protein degraders, is a recent emerging therapeutic modality in drug discovery. PROTACs are heterobifunctional compounds that use potent cellular degradation machinery to destroy target proteins. PROTACs utilize the UPS (ubiquitin protease system), a cellular system responsible for protein degradation, to precisely eliminate target proteins. In a study written in 2001 and published by Professor Crews and Professor Deshaies, the idea of "PROTAC" was initially put forth. They created the first PROTAC molecule, protac-1, a chimeric chemical, to demonstrate the theory. When PROTAC-1 interacts with the target protein MetAp-2, it may "recruit" a unique E3 ligase complex of SCF β -TRCP, which then degrades MetAp-2 through the natural ubiquitin-proteasome degradation pathway [6-7]. A PROTAC is a small molecule consisting of two distinct regions: one binds to the target disease-causing protein marked for degradation, and the other binds to an E3 ubiquitin ligase within the cellular ubiquitin system. These regions are linked together [8]. Linkers fall into three main categories: flexible, relatively rigid, and click-chemistry-based linkers. Rigid linkers like alkyne, piperazine, and piperidine enhance PROTAC effectiveness and pharmacokinetics. Flexibility is improved by adding alkyl, PEG, or glycol chains. Click reactions and clickable linkers enhance self-assembly within cells, improving permeability. Astex Pharmaceuticals has developed smaller CLIPTACs for intracellular use [9].

When the PROTAC molecule binds to the target protein, it brings the E3 ubiquitin ligase into proximity, leading to the ubiquitination and subsequent degradation of the target protein by the cell's 26S proteasome machinery [10-12]. The structure of PROTACs can vary depending on the intended target protein and the E3 ligase being used. PROTACs can be divided into two classes: heterobifunctional and homobifunctional. Heterobifunctional PROTACs consist of two different ligands, one that binds to the target protein and the other that binds to the E3 ligase. In contrast, homobifunctional PROTACs consist of two identical ligands that bind to the target protein and the E3 ligase [13]. The mechanism of action of PROTACs involves the recruitment of the E3 ubiquitin ligase to a specific protein, followed by the ubiquitination of the target protein. The ubiquitinated protein is then recognized by the proteasome, which degrades it into small peptides. The specificity of PROTACs is determined by the ligand used, and therefore, it is essential to design highly selective ligands to avoid off-target effects [Fig. 1] [14].

Fig. 1. Mechanism of Action of PROTAC

BIFUNCTIONAL SMALL MOLECULES

Bifunctional small molecules are utilised by PROTAC to enable the ubiquitination of specific proteins. These substances consist of two distinct functional groups, each of which interacts with a target in their unique way. For instance, one group may attach to a protein linked to an illness, while the other group regulates the protein's activity. Depending on their target, they can function as allosteric modulators, antagonists, agonists, or inhibitors of the target protein. Protein degradation is not directly caused by them. Rather, they regulate a target protein's activity, which may have an impact on cellular pathways later on [15]. They can target a wide range of illnesses, including cancer, hereditary diseases, and neurological disorders. They are extensively utilised for therapeutic purposes. Target protein activity is controlled by bifunctional small molecules, whereas PROTAC compounds cause the targeted protein to degrade [16–18]. In the process of finding and developing new drugs, both approaches have specific uses and modes of action. By employing a bifunctional technique that involves these molecules interacting with a portion of the proteostasis machinery and a protein of interest (POI), chemical biologists are now able to control the breakdown of proteins [19].

E3 LIGASES

A class of enzymes known as E3 ligases is responsible for the covalent attachment of ubiquitin molecules to proteins, changing those proteins. The altered protein is marked for proteasome breakdown by this process, which is referred to as ubiquitination. E3 ligases are in charge of identifying the place and quantity of ubiquitin molecules attached, as well as identifying and binding to particular target proteins, in order to ascertain the specificity of ubiquitination. Two ligands are included in PROTAC molecules: one binds to the target protein of interest, and the other binds to an E3 ligase. The target protein and the cellular machinery responsible for protein breakdown are connected by the E3 ligase component [20]. There are over 600 different types of E3 ligases, such as CRBN, VHL, MDM2, β -TRCP, cIAP, RNF4, RNF114, DCAF16, and KEAP1, but the majority of PROTAC technology uses four extremely effective E3 ligases: cellular inhibitors of apoptosis 1 (CIAP1), von Hippel Lindau (VHL), cereblon (CRBN), and mouse double minute 2 homolog (MDM2) [21]. Certain proteins, including tau protein, beta-amyloid, protein hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF), p53, and others, are degraded by these E3 ligases. PROTAC treatment has the ability to selectively degrade disease-causing proteins while sparing healthy ones by directing E3 ligases towards specific target proteins utilising PROTACs [22–23]. Considering that different E3 ligases have differing substrate specificities, selecting the right one is essential for PROTAC design. Choosing the right E3 ligase guarantees that the PROTAC molecule enlists and breaks down the intended target protein efficiently. Because they facilitate target protein ubiquitination and subsequent degradation, E3 ligases are essential to PROTAC technology. By allowing for selective and targeted protein breakdown, their incorporation into PROTAC molecules provides a potential therapeutic approach for illnesses whose targets are undruggable [24].

UPS (ubiquitin protease system)

The control of protein levels in cells is mostly dependent on the ubiquitin protease system, an essential biological mechanism. The complex web of proteins and enzymes that recognises and breaks down undesirable or harmed proteins is in charge. Since protein turnover is essential for synaptic plasticity and memory in the nervous system, it must be taken into account when controlling protein stability and function in neuronal cells. The UPS regulates most protein activities involved in the postsynaptic response in neuronal cells [25]. Targeting UPS is a distinct concept that is leading the way in medication discovery for many difficult diseases or disorders. Eukaryotic cells have an internal mechanism known as the UPS (Ubiquitin Proteasome System) that breaks down or eliminates proteins in a pathological state. This mechanism helps the body maintain cellular protein homeostasis by going through the ubiquitination process [26–27].

A cascade of three enzymes, including ubiquitin-activating enzymes (E1), ubiquitin-conjugating enzymes (E2), and substrate-specific ligases (E3), work together continuously to complete the three-step process of ubiquitination. By establishing a ubiquitin E1 thioester bond and activating the free ubiquitin (Ub) in an ATP-dependent manner, E1 then transfers the active Ub to E2 through trans-thioesterification. Finally, the E3 ligase recruits the ubiquitin-tagged E2 and target proteins to aid in labelling target proteins with ubiquitin. This type of ubiquitination can be repeated to produce poly-ubiquitin chain-tagged target proteins, thereby directing the marked proteins to the 26S proteasome for destruction [28–29]. The binding of ubiquitin molecules to the target protein is carried out by the E3 ubiquitin ligase. The proteasome is alerted to break down the protein by ubiquitin, which functions as a tag. The E3 ubiquitin ligase acts as a bridge molecule between the ubiquitin protease system and the target protein in PROTAC treatment [30].

Targeted protein degradation occurs when the PROTAC molecule binds an increasing number of E3 ubiquitin ligases, strengthening the degradation signal. This approach has shown promise in the treatment of cancer because it enables the targeted elimination of cancer-causing proteins, which results in the death of cells. The ubiquitin protease system is used in PROTAC therapy to specifically break down disease-causing proteins. This approach offers a more effective means of treating illnesses by reducing side effects and focusing on particular proteins. Understanding the

UPS in each neuron is essential to developing new therapeutic strategies that increase proteasomal degradation to remove harmful aggregates in neuronal cells [31].

Fig. 2. Application of PROTAC in drug development

PROTAC APPLICATION IN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

The build-up of tau and beta-amyloid proteins is believed to be a primary cause of neurodegeneration in Alzheimer's disease. In order to treat Alzheimer's disease, PROTACs have the ability to specifically break down these proteins and lessen their buildup in the brain. For example, the ligand domain of the PROTAC molecule allows it to attach itself to a target protein like beta-amyloid or Tau. By binding to an E3 ubiquitin ligase, the other PROTAC domain attracts ubiquitin molecules to the target protein. The proteasome uses these ubiquitin molecules as a signal to break down the target protein [32–33]. Due to their possible involvement in targeted protein breakdown, a number of E3 ligases have drawn interest. One such E3 ligase is CRBN (cereblon), which has been explored as a possible target in PROTAC (proteolysis-targeting chimaera) development. Another E3 ligase of interest is VHL (von Hippel-Lindau), known for its involvement in protein degradation pathways. Additionally, being researched as an E3 ligase for possible PROTAC-based therapies is MDM2 (mouse double minute 2) [34].

One of the most popular therapy targets for Alzheimer's is the tau protein. The disease-defining characteristic known as neurofibrillary tangles is linked to the accumulation and aggregation of tau. Another molecule receiving interest in PROTAC research is beta-amyloid protein, which causes plaques in the brains of Alzheimer's patients [35–36]. Another enzyme of interest in Alzheimer's research is glycogen synthase kinase 3 (GSK-3), which is involved in a number of cellular activities, including the phosphorylation of tau [37]. Finally, because of its function in cellular homeostasis and protein regulation, METAP-2 (methionine aminopeptidase 2) has been studied as a possible target [38].

The development of PROTACs that aim to promote targeted protein breakdown and potentially address important pathogenic pathways linked to Alzheimer's disease can be facilitated by these E3 ligases and molecules of interest. In preclinical research, PROTACs have demonstrated encouraging outcomes regarding Alzheimer's disease. For instance, in a study that was published in 2018 and 2021, new small-molecule PROTAC molecules called TH006 and C004019 are Tau-targeted PROTAC molecules that, in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease, recruit E3-ligase (VHL), significantly lower Tau levels, and avoid Tau-induced neuronal toxicity [39–40]. In conclusion, through a distinct underlying mechanism of action, PROTACs have the ability to specifically target and destroy disease-causing proteins implicated in Alzheimer's disease. To confirm these results and evaluate the safety and effectiveness of PROTACs as an Alzheimer's disease treatment, more clinical research is needed [Table 1] [41].

PROTAC APPLICATION IN CANCER TREATMENT

PROTACs' distinct mode of action has created a lot of interest in their potential as a cancer treatment. The uncontrolled proliferation and survival of cancer cells are frequently caused by the overexpression or mutation of proteins in cancer. A promising method to specifically break down these disease-causing proteins and stop the spread of cancer is to use PROTACs. A number of compounds have come to light in cancer research as potential targets for PROTAC-mediated protein degradation. Prostate cancer targets the androgen receptor (AR). The therapy of oestrogen receptor-positive breast cancer is being investigated with ER α -targeting PROTACs. The oestrogen receptor (ER α) is another area of study. The protein Bruton's tyrosine kinase (BTK) is of interest in B-cell malignancies, and PROTACs targeting BTK could potentially inhibit cancer cell growth. The bromodomain and extra terminal domain (BET) family of proteins, including BRD3, BRD4, and BRD9, are also significant targets due to their involvement in various cancers. Furthermore, PROTAC-mediated degradation in cancer and other disorders has drawn attention to the cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) protein family and signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3). PROTACs provide an intriguing strategy for targeted protein degradation and potential treatments in various research fields. These E3 ligases, such as cereblon (CRBN), von Hippel-Lindau (VHL), and inhibitor of apoptosis proteins (IAPs), have been successfully used for designing PROTAC compounds and the identification of pertinent point-of-interest molecules [42–43].

For instance, BRD4 (Bromodomain-containing protein 4), BCL2 (B-cell Leukemia/lymphoma 2), and EGFR (epidermal growth factor receptor) are among the oncogenic proteins that PROTACs are intended to target. One transcriptional regulator essential to the survival and growth of cancer cells is BRD4. Preclinical investigations have demonstrated that a PROTAC molecule degrades BRD4 in cancer cells by binding to it and enlisting the help of an E3 ubiquitin ligase. This inhibits the proliferation of cancer cells. Similarly, cancer often overexpresses the anti-apoptotic protein BCL2, which prevents programmed cell death. In preclinical research, it has been demonstrated that PROTACs targeting BCL2 preferentially degrade BCL2 and cause apoptosis in cancer cells, resulting in decreased tumour growth and higher survival. Lastly, uncontrolled growth and metastasis are caused by the overexpression or mutation of the EGFR receptor, which occurs frequently in cancer. It has been demonstrated in preclinical research that PROTACs that target EGFR can specifically degrade the receptor and prevent the growth and spread of cancer cells. By specifically targeting and degrading disease-causing proteins, PROTACs present a fresh and promising avenue for cancer therapy. Targeting oncogenic proteins and stopping the spread of cancer have showed encouraging outcomes in preclinical research. To assess their safety and effectiveness in clinical trials, more research is necessary [44–45]. There are some protacs that crossed preclinical studies and entered clinical studies. Arvinas-developed ARV-110 targets AR, while ARV-471 targets ER, both of which have entered Phase II clinical studies. Early clinical trials have effectively shown their fundamental safety and efficacy [46-48]. The outcome of Phase III clinical trials, which are expected to be utilised in the treatment of prostate cancer and breast cancer, respectively, is the stage of their development [Table 1] [8].

TABLE. 1.

PROTAC	E3 ligase	Targeted protein	Indications
ARV-110	CRBN	BRD4	Prostate cancer [46]
ARV-471	VHL	AR	Breast cancer [47]
MZ1	VHL	BRD4	Leukaemia [49]
dBET1	CRBN	BET, BRD4	Apoptosis [50]
SIAIS178	VHL	BCR-ABL	Anticancer activity [51]
ARV-825	CRBN	BRD4	Breast cancer [52]
ARV-771	VHL	BRD4	Prostate cancer [53]
SNIPER(ABL)-020	IAP	BCR-ABL	Cancer [54]
ARD-61	VHL	AR	Cancer [55]
ARD-266	VHL	AR	Cancer [56]
ARD-69	VHL	AR	Prostate cancer [57]
SD-36	CRBN	STAT3	Blood cancer [58]
dBET6	CRBN	BET	Antitumor activity [59]
ACB11	VHL	SMARCA2, SMARCA4, PBRM1	Anti-proliferative [60]
dBIRD9	CRBN	BRD9	Anti-proliferative [61]

MD-224	CRBN,MDM2	p53	Cancer [62]
dCBP-1	CRBN	p300/CBP	Multiple myeloma [63]
PROTAC ER α Degradier-2	IAP	ER α	Cancer [64]
PROTAC FAK degrader 1	VHL	FAK	Cancer [65]
MS432	VHL	MEK1, MEK2	Cancer [66]

Table 1: Some efficient PROTACs

E3 ligases and Target proteins: Cereblon (CRBN), Von Hippel-Lindau (VHL), Mouse double minute 2 (MDM2), inhibitor of apoptosis proteins (IAP). Targeted protein: Bromodomain-containing protein 4 (BRD4), Androgen receptor (AR), Bromodomain and extra terminal protein (BET), Signal Transducer and Activator of Transcription 3 (STAT3), Bromodomain-containing protein 9 (BRD9), Estrogen receptor α (ER α), Focal Adhesion Kinase (FAK), mitogen-activated extracellular signal-regulated kinase (MEK). Tumor suppressor protein (p53).

DISEASES AND MEDICAL CONDITIONS WHERE PROTAC TECHNOLOGY IS BEING USED FOR DRUG DEVELOPMENT

1. Autoimmune disorders: PROTAC technology is being used to target a number of autoimmune diseases, including psoriasis, systemic lupus erythematosus, and rheumatoid arthritis, with the purpose of developing new drugs.
2. Neurodegenerative diseases: Huntington's disease, Parkinson's disease, and Alzheimer's disease are among the neurodegenerative conditions for which PROTAC technology is being employed to develop treatments.
3. Infectious diseases: Research is being done on PROTAC technology as a possible treatment for infections including chronic hepatitis B.
4. Genetic diseases: PROTAC technology targets disease-causing proteins for degradation, which may be used to treat genetic abnormalities [36].

Even though the field of PROTAC is expanding quickly, most of these treatments are still in the early stages of development and have not yet entered clinical trials.

ADVANTAGES OF PROTAC THERAPY

A promising biomedical research strategy called PROTAC (Proteolysis Targeting Chimaeras) therapy is being used to provide targeted protein degradation-based treatments for a variety of diseases. Compared to conventional medications, PROTAC therapy has the advantage of fewer off-target effects, enhanced specificity, and the capacity to target protein breakdown selectively.

PROTAC therapy may provide a novel approach to treating a number of illnesses, including cancer, autoimmune disorders, and neurological disorders. It has the ability to target previously undruggable proteins and genetic targets. Furthermore, PROTAC technology may contribute to the generation of treatments with improved safety profiles and extended efficacy.

Comparing PROTAC treatment to conventional drug development yields significant advantages. First of all, instead of merely blocking the activity of disease-causing proteins, it permits their selective destruction. Second, there is a lower chance of medication resistance developing because PROTAC treatment breaks down protein targets inside of cells. Its capacity to target and destroy disease-causing proteins within cells presents a promising avenue for treating a variety of illnesses [67].

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

PROTAC (Proteolysis Targeting Chimaeras) treatment is a targeted protein degradation-based therapeutic technique that has potential, but it also has limitations and a number of difficulties. Creating efficient PROTAC molecules is one of the main obstacles. Target proteins that are effectively recruited by PROTACs for proteasomal breakdown are distinct molecular configurations. The process of creating these kinds of compounds can be difficult and challenging, frequently including a lot of trial and error in order to optimise.

An additional challenge is the possibility of off-target consequences. PROTACs may interact with other proteins or cellular components, even though their intended target is a specific protein. This could result in undesirable effects that could restrict the use of PROTACs in clinical settings. Furthermore, PROTAC treatment is severely limited by the intrinsic complexity of the proteasome system [68].

The proteasome is a complex and highly controlled component of cellular machinery that is involved in numerous cellular processes and is essential in the turnover of proteins. A major difficulty is to design PROTAC compounds that can target individual proteins within this intricate network in an efficient and targeted manner. Lastly, because the process of developing and approving new therapeutic agents can be difficult and time-consuming, PROTAC treatment

faces regulatory obstacles. Because of this, it might take a few years before PROTACs are widely accessible for usage in clinical settings. PROTACs offer tremendous therapeutic potential, but there are many obstacles and restrictions in the way of their development and use [8,41].

CONCLUSION

When it comes to creating targeted protein degradation-based treatments for a range of illnesses, such as cancer and Alzheimer's, PROTAC therapy has shown great promise. Therapeutic medicines that are very effective and have few side effects are developed by the selective destruction of disease-causing proteins. The development of aberrant protein regulation-related brain plaque formation in Alzheimer's patients is essential for the disease's progression. In preclinical investigations, PROTACs that aim to trigger the breakdown of tau and β -amyloid proteins have demonstrated encouraging outcomes. PROTAC-based medicines have demonstrated significant efficacy in cancer treatment by targeting oncogenic factors and causing the degradation of tumour suppressor proteins, which effectively inhibits the growth of tumours. Notably, PROTACs have expanded the possibilities for cancer medication research by being designed to target undruggable targets like transcription factors. Though drug design and regulatory approval remain obstacles for PROTAC therapy, the potential advantages of these highly specialised and adaptable therapeutic modalities make PROTACs a promising possibility for the treatment of cancer and Alzheimer's disease. The progress of PROTACs holds great potential for a range of medical applications, making them a key area of interest for future research and development.

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